

Time Management and Task Prioritization

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ABSTRACT

In all professional fields, but especially medicine, time management and task prioritization are major skills and their importance cannot be over-stated. These skills, later in careers, become major factors in determining professional development and career success. These skills are especially important for medical students as the methods they develop in medical school are used through out their careers but there is very little structured time devoted, if any, to this skill. Medical college curricula generally do not have official courses for these topics. This article aims to provide a medical student or an early medical professional with some time management techniques that help reduce the work load. The important areas that mostly need attention in time management are goal setting, setting priorities, planning/organizing and minimizing time wasters.

1 Introduction

Task management and Task Prioritization are two extremely important skills and help a student guide their limited time and energies to the most important tasks first.

One of the most well known and generally accepted time management technique is the Stephen R. Covey's Time Management Matrix Technique (TMMT) [1]. This technique uses a four-quadrant table to group tasks based on their relative urgency and importance.

	Important	Less Important
Urgent	I Answering urgent pages about patients. Physical examinations. Ordering labs and imaging.	III Answering parent questions. Attending teaching sessions.
Less Urgent	II Discharge planning. Daily notes.	IV Answering personal emails. Reading about patients. Studying for board examinations.

Figure 1: Stephen R. Covey's TMMT Example [1]

2 The How

Below are some of the techniques that can be used to properly manage time.

2.1 Goal Setting

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Figure 2: Showing a sample dashboard with progress tracking towards goals.

2.2 Setting Priorities

Setting priorities in a world full of opportunities and, unfortunately, of distractions is a key skill every professional should develop. There are two kinds of responsibilities:

2.2.1 New Responsibilities

A physician's daily life includes managing patients, teaching medical students and making time for hobbies. For a student, working with doctors, studying and some down-time make

up the day. Successful time management means separating the most important and fruitful tasks from the ones that are not as beneficial. This is also the part where TMMT is helpful. If a task is important and urgent, it should be taken care of first but success lies in completing the important but less urgent tasks as well like writing a research proposal which is optional for the student.

Some students have tests in medical college and preparing for them takes up a lot of the available time. The solution here is to use active learning and minimize the use of low yield study techniques.

Some responsibilities might be given to the student by a physician or their medical school. These types of responsibilities cannot be refused and must be added to the important and urgent box. This could be a problem if there are too many tasks in this column. The solution is to try to complete these as efficiently as possible and try to make time for other activities.

The goal is to make time for the activities that are important for the student's long term goals but are not time critical. Failure to do so results in time spent only in the most important and most urgent block which might hinder long term success.

2.2.2 Existing Responsibilities

Many of the points mentioned in 1 apply here as well. If a student already has too much responsibility, they might be able to delegate some tasks to their peers. They could also try talking to the physician giving them the responsibility and politely apologize to new responsibilities or ask to reduce the work load. Many physicians are considerate in this regard and would love to help as much as they can.

2.3 Planning/Organizing

After recognizing the most important tasks, the question now is how to most efficiently complete those tasks. One very important factor is the use of high yield study resources and study techniques [3]. Another major factor in determining the student's efficiency is when they complete the most demanding tasks.

Morningness and Eveningness are two terms defined in chronobiology which significantly affect the performance of students [4].

It is also important to create and plan tasks for at least a week. This gives an overview to the student as to what is important and what is coming up in the week. This also saves time as planning everyday is a tedious task and planning a week is much more efficient.

2.4 Minimizing Time Wasters

So much time everyday is lost to common time wasters and this article aims to provide some solutions. Table 1 lists some common time wasters and their possible solutions.

Ten common time wasters and potential solutions	
Time Waster	Proposed Solution
Telephone Calls	Check messages and return calls 1-2 times per day only.
Email	Check no more than 1-2 times per day. Disable notifications.
Physical Interruptions	Try to study in a quiet place like the university library or close the room door.
Paper	Handle each paper once. Make scanned copies and digitally tag them for easy search and access.
Repetitive Activities	Create 'quick text' that automatically expands to full text. Use softwares to help plan, organize and execute as much as possible.
Disorganization	Clean living and study space. See also paper distractions.
Procrastination	Identify and address reasons for procrastination. Accomplish small tasks and use milestones to track progress. Do not allow perfectionism to get in the way.
Meetings	Always be on time. Bring alternate work if others are not punctual.
Waiting	Perform quick and small tasks like checking in on calls and messages, listening to a podcast etc.
Commuting	Enjoy music (for relaxation), listen to audio books, learn a foreign language. Read journal articles if not driving.

Figure 3: Ten common time wasters and their possible solutions. Adapted for students from [0] Table 3.

3 References

[0] Some headings and the structure of the content in this article were borrowed from: Gordon CE, Borkan SC. Recapturing time: a practical approach to time management for physicians. *Postgrad Med J*. 2014 May;90(1063):267-72. doi: 10.1136/postgradmedj-2013-132012. Epub 2014 Mar 5. PMID: 24599633.

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